

The design development of a “Serious” board game – mediating the tension between playing the game and modelling experience for the purpose of gathering information.

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Abstract:

As part of the SEED project a serious game was designed to help a service user group based in a Psychiatric Unit to influence the redesign of their hospital environment. This consultation tool can be adapted to suit diverse contexts and applications.

The paper will examine the tension between designing a game that elicits pleasure and enjoyment from the participants and stimulates discussion and interaction which can supply useful information gathering when working with marginalised participants and those who have difficulty communicating their emotional responses in conventional consultation processes.

We will demonstrate that the game format can be a useful tool to facilitate clearer communication between professionals and marginalised user groups, such as designers and mental health service users and present the design development of the game from the initial concept through to application in other healthcare contexts and projects.

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Full paper:

This paper is about the SEED project and describes the application of the Game as a tool for meaningful consultation with a challenging and marginalised service user group. SEED is an acronym for supportive environments encouraging development. The name stresses the importance of valuing the service user perspective by providing a supportive environment to facilitate the development of skills for independent living and eventual discharge from hospital. There is evidence of a significant relationship between a hospital environment and the therapeutic care of psychiatric in-patients. (Karlín, Zeiss 2006) The SEED approach acknowledges this by involving people in the design process of their own healing environment. Initially the project was established to involve mental health service users in the consultation process for the design of a new low secure unit in the North West of England. Low Secure Units provide care for patients with serious mental disorders who require the provision of security. The principles and methodology used in the SEED project as a whole has been well documented. (Lamey, Bristow 2006) There is a growing body of evidence that demonstrates the importance of meaningful service user involvement in the design and planning of their healthcare settings. (Lawson, Phiri, 2003) Where it does take place, service user involvement in healthcare design is often hollow and superficial. “Consultation needs to be easily accessible and creative. It is important for people involved in the design process to seek out the views of service users, rather than expecting service users fit in with a timetable of long meetings.” (MIND 2006) A conventional approach is to invite a token service user to attend formal planning meetings, where they can feel intimidated by the formal procedures and the language of design and healthcare professionals. However, the SEED project has established a methodology that has empowered the service users and encouraged their inclusion in developing design proposals for the environment in which they live. (Lamey, Bristow 2006) The significance of the project is that it involves service users in the decision making and the design process. The project recognises the importance of providing a connection between service users and people with the skill and knowledge to help them develop their own thinking and to explore the options. As a result it aims to enable better communication between stakeholders in the design process – clinicians, estates managers, designers, architects, and of course the patient or service user. A range of approaches was utilised to engage the service users in the process, starting with a simple board game. Called the Project Planner Game, it was designed to help the group to look at their surroundings in an informal way and to encourage discussion about

the kind of environment that they found most helpful towards their recovery. The advantage of the “game” format is that it is familiar and reassuring. It is a creative approach to a serious issue.

Board games in this type of context can be used to introduce a topic in a fun, unthreatening way that builds trust, co-operation and honest responses.

(www.universalboardgames.co.uk) Games can be used to contact deep emotions. The SEED Game (© 2008 Lancashire Care NHS Trust) can be loosely termed a story telling game i.e. the main activity of the game is conversation. It is a race game with a theme, but unlike many conventional board games, it is not important to have a game strategy, and the game is deliberately non-confrontational and collaborative. (Gobet et al 2004) It can also be referred to as a “serious” game – a phrase used in the Games industry to identify computer games that have a useful outcome or that model real life situations. (Purdy 2007) Serious games are “not entertainment products but items that use entertainment to achieve a purpose, such as training.” (www.seriousgames.org). This game is deliberately not a computer game, since one of the primary aims is to engender conversation, and interaction between the service user group, the healthcare staff and the designers/architects or other external consultants. The game is a starting point to the design process. The outcomes of the game inform the design brief or the consultation. The game is one of a number of design activities that could be used to illicit information from client groups. However, some service users are not comfortable filling in questionnaires, they are perhaps not confident about their written skills, or do not understand the context and need the help of a facilitator.

Examples exist of games that are used in similar contexts and with comparable aims and objectives. Universal Board Games is a partnership based in London, UK who use board games as a tool to work with children and young people to enable them “to express themselves in fun, creative and innovative ways. One of their past projects (2007) called Transition Rollercoaster worked with young people moving from Primary education to Secondary education to explore the emotional turmoil of fears and worries they experience in the change of schools. In game design workshops they work with the children to develop their ideas into a game that can be used with other children who are going through the same experience. In 2005 UBG used board game playing as a tool to help Arsenal football team to consult with young people about the future of the Emirates Stadium podium and Eden Groves public spaces. The work that UBG undertake is inventive, creative and innovative. They use the activity of playing games to engage with a difficult target group and then use their results to develop new games that can be used to

communicate with other groups, for example to feedback views to other stakeholders, such as local government and board members. (www.universalboardgames.co.uk).

A new game designed by RIBA uses the game format to engage with primarily adult groups within local communities, both professional (architects and planners) and amateur (councillors, community groups). Building Futures is an example of a serious game concept used as a tool to explore different options for future plans in a location. It is designed to open up dialogue between various groups at the start of planning, regeneration or development process. Ideas and other findings which are revealed by the game process are used as the basis for further consultation and community involvement. Games have also been used within healthcare contexts as a tool for communication between clinicians and patients, for example, a Design Council team worked with Bolton Primary Care Trust to develop a pack of cards to help patients with diabetes to manage their condition. Clinicians recognised that people with diabetes find it difficult to change their lifestyle and eating habits. Health workers had previously used questionnaires to gather information about lifestyle and eating patterns, but a new approach was needed to encourage individuals to take control of their own condition and to enable better communication between patients and their healthcare providers. The “need” cards are arranged into four themed “suits” and communicate real life examples of the feelings and emotions experienced by diabetes sufferers, for example: “Sometimes the medical terms confuse me”, “I worry about coping at parties”, and “This diabetes has taken over”. The cards are used by patients during medical consultations to help them to express their own feelings about their condition. Jenny Winhall from the Design Council team said that “The cards would help to bring out dimensions of their lives previously hidden to care givers, providing the flexibility for patients to define their own diabetes care agenda.” (www.designcouncil.org.uk/en/Case-Studies/All-Case-Studies/RED---Diabetes-/Service-development/)

In each of these examples the game is used to facilitate communication and consultation between disparate groups, often where the power relationship is imbalanced, such as between a doctor and a patient, or a planner and a resident. The SEED Game (© 2008 Lancashire Care NHS Trust) facilitates a dialogue between service users, healthcare staff, designers, researchers, academics, and other external consultants. The mixture of skills and backgrounds make for a unique combination of designers, healthcare workers and service users. This is an unprecedented approach within mental health care which enables the collaborators to engage with each other on a different level where position and status are immaterial.

The first version of the game was produced in a simple, temporary format by Carol Bristow to be used as an ice breaker-type activity to facilitate discussion with the service user group about the design of a new low secure unit. This version was made of square painted cardboard. There is a prize for the winner, and most importantly everyone takes a turn to answer a question and thereby contribute to the information gathered. It allows patients to share their feelings and emotions and discuss their hospital environment with reference to their own experience. Players identify for themselves the important components of an effective healthcare environment by asking questions such as “How should a building feel?” alongside questions about the more functional issues such as the use of space and security needs. Questions prompt the players to reflect on issues such as space, colour, and function. There is a facilitator, whose role is fundamentally important to the success of the activity, but the game is not hierarchical. The players choose where to start, and everyone joins in, facilitator, architect, academic, nurse, and service user. The emphasis at this early stage in the SEED project was on awareness raising amongst the service users, who were not used to being asked about the design of their hospital environment, and didn’t have the language and knowledge to contribute in conventional ways. Some service users are not comfortable with questionnaires or discussion groups. One player said of the game that it: “Gives a say in what we do. It’s an ice breaker. Otherwise people sat there not knowing what to say. It opened my mind – opened doors. It gave me ideas about design.” The second adaptation of the game was developed with the SEED group, who planned, made and painted the board themselves. This version was made to be more adaptable, in that the questions could be changed to reflect the needs and themes of a range of consultation needs and stages of the process. It was successfully used to facilitate a number of discussions with a changing group of service users to obtain feedback on a number of developments within the unit, for example, the transition from smoking to non-smoking in the hospital, and the provision of seclusion (or extra care) on the unit.

In October 2007 a grant was received from the National Endowment of Science, Technology and the Arts (NESTA) as part of their Innovations in Mental Health challenge to support the development of the game into a product for dissemination to other projects and contexts. The question was could a game be developed as a research tool to evaluate user-choices and aspirations in a variety of contexts? A programme of activities was planned to research, review and test the concept. With the help of a small project team and regular consultations with the service user group at significant stages of the process, a number of objectives were set.

The team aimed to evaluate the format, rules, and look of the game, assess the role of the facilitator, test the game in other contexts and with other types of service user groups, for example, people with learning disabilities, children, and the elderly with dementia, and to investigate the potential for a digital version of the game. It was also important to consider practical issues such as how to produce the board in a lightweight material, develop a prototype, explore links with manufacturers, look at branding and marketing the product, and develop a business plan to market the final design.

Working with game designers from the University of Central Lancashire, the team reviewed the game as it had been originally developed. They threw everything up in the air and started from scratch, wishing to pinpoint the essential and fixed aspects of the original game and identify the core key features. Asking questions such as, what is the ultimate aim of the game? Is there a way of winning? How do you record comments? And, is there a formal summarising at the end? It was recognised that the visual appearance was fundamental to the success of the game. “How do we make it approachable, serious and fun?” There is a point between ‘yet another boring simulation game’ and ‘doesn’t look serious enough to give it thought’. Good games offer a variety of strategy options to players. Some of these strategies are not always immediately apparent to the novice and only after several play sessions may they become apparent. To add to this complexity game strategies often offer subtle advantages and disadvantages depending on the current state of play. In general it is the discovery and mastery of these game strategies in order to successfully complete a game that provides the mental stimulus, entertainment and reward for playing a game. In the design of this game it quickly became apparent that these factors far from being a boon to the game could potentially form a barrier to the involvement of the intended users and facilitators. There is always a tension between a tool that models experience and a fun game. It is important that the project planner game does both. If the game successfully achieves this aim, then it is doubly worthwhile.

The shape and layout of the game field was discussed and a number of different layouts were tested. It was assumed by the designers that a circular design would be more holistic and inclusive to the players, but the service users were happier with the more commonly used rectangular format. As part of the process the team had game playing workshops, to experience the game mechanics of other less serious games. Ideas were considered for complex, multi-layered, detailed approaches, such as collecting “seeds”, or building models, or having wheels and compartments in the board. However it was recognised that the design should not be too complex or challenging, since many of the

target groups have short concentration spans and players might need to dip in and out of the game.

Fundamental to the game is the quality of the questions. In order to elicit discussion (an important aim of the game) the questions need to be open ended, avoiding questions that will only elicit one word answers, or “yes” and “no”. Not “What colour would you like your bedroom.” But “What sort of colours might help you relax and sleep better?” The team developed a number of possible layouts for the game board, and had them printed out onto fabric. In order not to confuse the issue the layouts used no images or colours. The game was played in different contexts and with different players and types of service users to test out some of the ideas and assumptions established by the game design team. Feedback from these sessions was formative, both in reinforcing previous findings, and in presenting unexpected information. A Mental Health Service Advocate played the game with a group of service users and observed that “Only two players were ready to play. However, it was great that other players could come in and out so easily. In the end 5 patients contributed to the session.....I felt the momentum of the game dip after about 40 minutes.” The facilitator observed that she felt there was a natural excitement building up towards the end of the game, despite the fact that some people had come and gone. She said, “The answers were fascinating and the game kept the issues focused.” This echoed the experience of playing the game with similar mental health service users. The service users liked that the first player chooses where the game starts and the rules are easily picked up because of the standard board game format which made it accessible to the players. New suggestions were for introducing topic appropriate counters, for example a megaphone, a telephone or a pair of lips, and it would be helpful to have a set of standard mood cards that accompany the game and work on a generic level with the middle questions. “Possibly even use a ‘feel-wheel’ showing a spectrum of feelings” for the players to use to help communicate their emotions. This suggestion matched well with the way in which the design team were thinking about the game, that it is important to give credence to the player’s emotions as well as their opinions, but that players might not have the words for either. It is difficult to communicate about visual things with words and words can be ambiguous. (Arnheim 1970) We may use the same terminology, but mean different things, since colour is a product of our brains and we don’t always see the same things. (Fletcher 2001) Colours can be most easily conveyed by pointing at a swatch or colour wheel. The idea of collecting mood cards as part of the game was introduced to help players visualise the ideas they had about their environment. However, it was felt that this might become a secondary activity, a follow up to the main game, so

as not to over complicate the rules or confuse the players. Following the feedback from the game trials, it was decided to have two types of questions, board questions that ask what the player knows or thinks and middle questions that ask what the player feels. The middle questions might include words, colours or images that players might use as visual prompts to show their emotional and pragmatic responses.

It was important to test how important the role of the facilitator was to the successful outcome of the game. In the early iterations the SEED project leader always took the role of facilitator. It was important to observe and record how she acted, what she did in order to develop rules and instructions for other facilitators. It was also useful to record how other people undertook the facilitation role. Was it different? One facilitator said that it was hard work to play, encourage, question and record answers and suggested that there should be two facilitators for the game. Draft guidelines were drawn up which aim to clearly set out the focus for any facilitation role. Primarily the guidelines emphasise that the aim of the game is to collect information, so the facilitator should be clear about what they are trying to achieve from the game process. They need to understand their players/audience and what results they are trying to achieve. One of the most important sections refers to “interaction”. Facilitators are advised to “Promote the game session before the event. Introduce the game concept by publishing information i.e. posters or leaflets, etc. Make the event special. Identify roles and responsibilities for the participants. Use quality materials. Let the group have ownership of the game. Ensure the game subject is relevant to the participants needs. Provide opportunities to learn new skills. Provide opportunities to be heard and valued. Provide opportunities to share their unique experiences and expertise.” The guidelines stress the importance of the player’s perspective. The facilitator is an enabler, who encourages the participants to find their own solutions and ideas.

In developing prototypes of this game the question “Does consideration x invite or bar involvement in the game by the intended users?” became one of the most relevant factors in any design decision.

In typical board games the joy of participation and achievement are generally sufficient in engaging players. The game in itself does not need any greater meaning or outcome. In the development of this game it became apparent from the play testing that as well as these familiar aspects to any game that it was very important that the overall achievement of the discussion and contribution i.e. a clearer view of the design issues the game is eliciting responses to, needed to be made manifest to the participants. This gave the game

value as a tool and also underlined the value of the client's contribution to the larger design development exercise.

The level of development of many modern board games is very sophisticated in terms of components and methods of play. During the initial planning stage many of these new types of games were considered. However, it soon became evident that the majority of the experiences of the intended users and facilitators were limited to more familiar traditional board games. In developing this type of game it was discovered that for it to be accepted by the potential facilitators then it should not make too much demand on them to learn a 'new' style of game. This was one of the major factors in deciding upon a travel round the board format for the game.

The rules for playing this game have been consciously left simple and open to some interpretation. During play-testing it appeared that in running the game the facilitator and users had to feel comfortable in introducing mutually agreed variations, sometimes within a single play session, in order to let the game flow in a positive manner.

At this stage the game is considered as being suitable for all and may be considered a basis from which more complex games might be approached. The development of more complex games might be desirable in order to deal with different and diverse client groups, facilitator's experience and wider design issues that may be considered.

In all of the development considerations of the SEED Game (© 2008 Lancashire Care NHS Trust) the most important aspect of the design is that it should promote insightful discussion and input from the clients in a manner that can be recorded and used by the facilitator. Even though the current game has a very traditional format the questions used and the conversation it provokes lies at the heart of its suitability for promoting useful design discussion amongst marginalised user groups.

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